

THE IMPACT OF EMPLOYMENT STATUS ON DIETARY HABITS: TEACHERS vs HOMEMAKERS

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Abstract

In contemporary Indian society, women increasingly balance professional responsibilities with domestic roles, influencing their dietary habits and health outcomes. This study explores how employment status affects food choices, dietary patterns, and nutritional status among women aged 25–45 in Telangana, India, by comparing working women (teachers) with homemakers. A cross-sectional quantitative design was employed, involving 150 participants (75 from each group) selected through convenience sampling. Data were collected using structured questionnaires and analysed using SPSS Version 24. Significant differences were observed between the two groups. Working women reported greater time constraints, leading to increased reliance on ready-to-eat foods ($p=0.002$) and differences in meal planning ($p=0.007$). Homemakers faced barriers related to access and affordability but were more likely to engage in traditional food preparation ($p=0.002$). Motivations for dining choices also differed significantly ($p=0.007$). Supplement use varied by purpose ($p<0.001$) and frequency ($p=0.004$), reflecting differing health priorities and access. BMI analysis showed that 43.9% had a normal BMI, while 26.5% were overweight and 12.9% obese. Regarding meal patterns, 67.7% of participants consumed three meals daily, 54.8% had early breakfasts, and 42.6% dined out 1–3 times per week. These findings underscore clear distinctions in nutrition-related behaviours influenced by employment status. The study emphasizes the need for targeted, employment-sensitive nutritional interventions that address time constraints, economic factors, and cultural food practices to improve women's health outcomes in diverse socio-economic contexts.

Keywords: Nutrition behaviour, women's health, dietary habits, employment status, BMI, supplement use, traditional food practices, barriers, facilitators.

Introduction

In modern Indian society, women's dual roles as professionals and homemakers significantly shape their dietary habits and health outcomes. With growing female participation in the workforce, particularly in education, women face increasing time constraints that affect meal planning, food choices, and nutritional balance. Conversely, homemakers, while seemingly having more time for food preparation, often confront challenges related to affordability, access, and social expectations. Employment status influences not only time availability but also dietary behaviours, food purchasing decisions, and traditional cooking practices. Urbanization, changing lifestyles, and exposure to convenience foods have further complicated women's nutrition, leading to a rise in obesity, metabolic disorders, and other health issues. These dynamics are especially pronounced among women aged 25–45 a group navigating both reproductive and career-related responsibilities. This study examines the impact of employment on the dietary patterns, nutritional status, and supplement use among working women (teachers) and non-working women (homemakers) in Telangana. It identifies barriers such as time, cost, and access, and facilitators like nutritional awareness and family support, to understand how daily routines influence health. Addressing these differences is crucial to developing employment-sensitive nutritional strategies that promote better health outcomes for Indian women.

Objectives

- To analyze and compare meal timing, frequency of meals eaten outside the home, take-out meals between the two groups.
- To evaluate and compare the nutritional status of non working and working women through anthropometric measurements.
- To identify and compare the perceived barriers (lack of time, cooking skills, access to healthy foods)
- To identify and compare the facilitators (nutrition knowledge, social support) to adopting and maintaining healthy eating habits in both groups.
- To evaluate the use of supplement vs traditional nutrition practices in both groups

Review Of Literature:

A growing body of research highlights the multifaceted relationship between women's employment status, education, and dietary behaviours. Assumpção et al. (2018) emphasized that while employment plays a role in shaping dietary habits, education level has a more pronounced effect on diet quality. Their study found that low-educated homemakers consumed significantly fewer fruits, vegetables, and whole grains compared to their working counterparts, indicating that nutritional disparities are often rooted in educational inequality. Complementing this, Dhir et al. (2020) established that working women, due to limited time and lifestyle demands, are more likely to consume processed and convenience foods, resulting in elevated BMI, waist-hip ratios, and lipid profiles thus increasing their risk of non-communicable diseases. Similarly, Akshatha (2023) noted a contrast wherein working women demonstrated higher levels of nutritional awareness but lacked consistency in traditional food practices, which remained stronger among homemakers.

Lima et al. (2021) further explored the workplace environment as a determinant of eating behaviour, revealing that university staff often cited time scarcity, food pricing, and lack of healthy options as barriers to nutritious eating. These findings align with Welch et al. (2009), who reported that 41% of women considered time pressure a significant barrier not only to healthy eating but also to engaging in physical activity particularly among those balancing work and domestic duties. Lastly, Wijayaratne et al. (2018) stressed the role of food literacy, arguing that women with greater nutritional knowledge, skills, and confidence are better equipped to navigate dietary challenges, adopt healthier food choices, and influence family nutrition positively. Together, these studies underline the complex interaction between employment, education, time, and food-related behaviour in shaping women's health outcomes.

These studies collectively suggest that while working women struggle with time, homemakers are constrained by resources both scenarios demand context-sensitive interventions.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study involved 150 women (75 working teachers and 75 homemakers) aged 25–45, selected through convenience sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire that assessed sociodemographic details, dietary habits, barriers and facilitators to healthy eating, supplement use, and traditional food practices. Women with specific medical conditions or dietary restrictions were excluded. Data analysis was performed using descriptive statistics, Independent Sample t-tests for BMI and eating-out frequency, and One-Way ANOVA for comparing meal frequency, convenience food reliance, and meal timing between groups.

Results And Discussion

ANOVA TABLE:

Variable Compared	F-Value	p-Value	Significance	Interpretation
1. Dining Motivations (Working vs non-working)	5.214	0.007	Significant	Employment status influences reasons for dining out (e.g., time, social context)
2. RTE Meal Frequency	6.242	0.002	Significant	Working women consume more RTE meals, likely due to time constraints
3. Meal Planning Frequency	5.136	0.007	Significant	Non-working women plan meals more consistently

Levene's Test For Equality Of Variances:

Barrier	F-Value	Sig. (p-value)	Interpretation
Lack of Time	0.006	0.940	Equal variances assumed – No significant difference in variance across groups.
Limited Cooking Skills	5.460	0.021	Equal variances not assumed – Significant difference in variance; group responses vary.
Cost of Healthy Foods	7.516	0.007	Equal variances not assumed – Significant variance difference between groups.
Family Preferences	0.252	0.616	Equal variances assumed – Variance is similar between the groups.
Access to Fresh Ingredients	7.619	0.007	Equal variances not assumed – Variability in responses differs significantly.

Facilitator	Two-Sided p-value	Interpretation
Family Support	0.003	Statistically significant difference – Employment status influences perceived family support.
Market Access	0.032	Statistically significant difference – Access to healthy food markets differs by group.
Nutrition Knowledge	0.046	Statistically significant difference – Working and non-working women differ in nutritional awareness.
Availability of Healthy Recipes	<0.001	Highly significant difference – Perception of access to healthy recipes varies significantly.
Positive Role Models	0.060	Not statistically significant – No meaningful difference in influence of role models across groups.

Conclusion

This study reveals that women's dietary choices are shaped less by preference and more by their social roles and access to resources. Employment status significantly influences these patterns working women struggle with time, while homemakers face affordability and access issues. These differences reflect broader gender-based inequalities. Promoting better nutrition must go hand-in-hand with addressing the structural barriers that impact women's health and well-being.

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